

1 **A cell death program in circulating tumor cells in human cancer governed by genes of the Bcl**
2 **family.**

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7 A hallmark of cancer cells is evasion of programmed cell death. We studied total transcription in circulating
8 tumor cells (CTC) isolated from the peripheral blood of humans with stage IV breast cancer. Silencing of
9 *Mcl1* was a defining characteristic of the CTC. Circulating tumor cells silenced or suppressed expression
10 of BCL apoptotic regulators *Bcl2l1*, *Bcl6*, *Bcl10*, and *BID*. Tumor cells in the peripheral blood
11 down-regulated the cell survival regulator *CFLAR*, IAP family genes *BIRC2* and *BIRC6*, as well as death
12 domain-containing molecules *FADD*, *DEDD* and *DEDD2*, while selectively activating caspase-14 and
13 *DNASE1*. An active cell death evasion and modulation program is evident in the circulating tumor cells of
14 humans with cancer.
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